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Executive Summary:

Renewable energy sources (RES) will play an important role in decarbonizing the electricity grid. However, high penetration of RES introduce new challenges to electrical power systems due to the variable and intermittent nature of energy production. Energy storage and flexible loads are ancillary services that can introduce reliability and resiliency to the electricity grid on a local scale. In this context, electrolysers have the potential to provide both energy storage and flexible loads through the production and storage of hydrogen. Moreover, hydrogen is considered an attractive and versatile alternative energy carrier due to its high calorific value and low environmental impact and it also can be exported as fuel to different markets.

Although electrolysers are an interesting option to provide ancillary services, batteries also have the potential to compete in the new system services market as a clean alternative for energy storage and balancing services. Thus, the current report aims to review the capability of electrolysers, most notably Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysers (PEME) and Alkaline Electrolysers (ALKE), to operate under variable conditions and to provide system services in Ireland. Furthermore, a technical-economic comparison of the potential of electrolysers and batteries to provide system services is presented.

Electrolysers have the ability to operate under variable conditions and to provide all system services categories as long as they keep operating at a minimum load. In the case of PEME the minimum load is a stand-by condition, while for ALKE is operating at around 20-25% load capacity. Both PEME and ALKE systems are reported to be able to vary their full load range from less than one second to few seconds. Warm start-up times for ALKE and PEME are up to 5 min and within seconds respectively, while cold start-up times are up to hours for ALKE and within minutes for PEME. The main advantages of PEME over ALKE is their higher load range and their lower sensitiveness to cycling. However, ALKE

are still cheaper and a technical-economic analysis of both technologies needs to be carried out while building a business case for electrolysers to be used in system services.

A technical-economic comparison between electrolysers and Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) was also carried out. Electricity storage with electrolysers is only limited by the hydrogen storage capacity while BESS are able to provide energy up to 6 hours. BESS have larger installed plants although no clear limitation exists for larger electrolyser plants deployment. Overall, the electrical efficiency of BESS is higher than for electrolysers systems. ALKE have the higher lifetime expectation followed by PEME. However, electrolysers and batteries subjected to dynamic loads is a recent topic and precise experimental data of degradation on these systems are still not available. CAPEX costs for ALKE, PEME and BESS are on average 870 EUR/kW, 1320 EUR/kW and 500 EUR/kWh respectively. OPEX is estimated to vary from 2 to 5% of CAPEX for electrolysers whereas for BESS is approximately 0.75% of its CAPEX.

List of Abbreviations

ALKE – Alkaline Electrolysers

BESS – Battery Energy Storage Systems

CAPEX – Capital Expenditure

OPEX – Operational Expenditure

PEME – Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysers

RES – Renewable Energy Sources

TSO – Transmission System Operator

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1 Introduction

Renewable energy sources (RES) will play an important role in decarbonizing the electricity grid. However, high penetration of RES introduce new challenges to electrical power systems due to the variable and intermittent nature of energy production. In other words, the fluctuation of energy production and possible mismatch between production and demand are introducing uncertainty regarding the resource requirements for maintaining power balance on the electricity grid. Thus, to bring about a substantial long-term penetration of RES and distributed energy resources, new tools, technologies and additional system services are necessary to provide the required level of system resiliency (Castillo & Gayme, 2014).

Energy storage and flexible loads are ancillary services that can introduce reliability and resiliency to the electricity grid on a local scale. Electricity storage can be used to inject energy to the grid when electricity production is lower than demand. While flexible loads can provide balancing services that can mitigate distribution line congestions due to overproduction of electricity (Mohanpurkar, et al., 2017). In this context, electrolysers have the potential to provide both electricity storage and flexible loads through the production and storage of hydrogen. Moreover, hydrogen is considered an attractive and versatile alternative energy carrier due to its high calorific value and low environmental impact and it also can be exported as fuel to different markets.

The interest of using electrolysers to provide grid balancing services is a recent topic which is currently under investigation among different groups (Allidières, et al., 2019). Eichman et al. explored the operational flexibility of electrolysers by performing experimental tests on Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysers (PEME) and Alkaline Electrolysers (ALKE). In their study, it was found that electrolysers are capable to participate in energy management on the utility scale and at end user facilities (Eichman, et al., 2014). Kiaee et al. simulated the application of a large scale ALKE used in hydrogen filling stations on a grid scenario with 25% penetration of wind power. Their results showed that the ALKE implementation can significantly reduce fluctuations in system frequencies (Kiaee, et al., 2014). Buttler & Spliethoff presented an overview of the current status of PEME, ALKE and solid oxide electrolysers in the context of energy storage, grid balancing and sector coupling via power-to-gas and power-to-liquid systems. The review provides a basis of the parameters required and the necessary understanding of electrolysis fundamentals and technologies for a techno-economic analysis of water electrolysis-based concepts (Buttler & Spliethoff, 2018). Hydrogenics in its Power-to-Hydrogen Expert training stated that a new stand-by mode for electrolyser has been developed that allows them to ramp-up from 0% to 100% output in less than 30 seconds. This performance meets the requirements to perform grid services in frequency regulation (Hydrogenics, 2019).

Although electrolysers are an interesting option to provide ancillary services, batteries also have the potential to compete in the new system services market as a clean alternative for energy storage and balancing services. Thus, the current report aims to review the capability of electrolysers, most notably PEME and ALKE, to operate under variable conditions and to provide system services in Ireland. Furthermore, a technical-economic comparison of the potential of electrolysers and batteries to provide system services is presented. The investigation was mainly carried out using the results of publicly available literature.

The report is divided into 5 sections: Section 1 explains the context of the current report; Section 2 reviews typical specifications of ALKE and PEME and their capability to provide system services; Section 3 presents a technical-economic comparison of the potential of electrolysers and batteries to provide system services; Section 4 discusses the results and recommendations for future clean system services designs.

2 Electrolysers capability to provide system services

Electrolysers are essentially electrochemical devices that consists of circulating a direct current through water to separate its molecules into hydrogen and oxygen. The configuration of an electrolytic cell consists of a pair of electrodes, an electrolyte and the diaphragm. The electrolysis process requires the implementation of a diaphragm or separator to avoid the recombination of the hydrogen and the oxygen generated at the electrodes (Ursua, et al., 2012). The global electrolysis reaction is presented in Eq. 1 and a representation of a proton exchange membrane electrolysis cell is shown in **Figure 1**.

An electrolyser, or an electrolytic hydrogen production plant, includes additional equipment. The hydrogen and oxygen generated are cooled, purified, compressed or liquified, and stored. In many installations, the oxygen is not stored but vented to the atmosphere instead. Furthermore, there are also electrolysers that produce hydrogen at very high pressure, thus avoiding the compression stage, however this method is more costly and energy demanding (Ursua, et al., 2012).

Figure 1 – Diagram of the operating principle of a proton exchange membrane electrolysis cell.

2.1 Typical specification of electrolysers

Currently, there are two main commercially available technologies of electrolysers (ALKE and PEME). Aiming to compare both electrolyser technologies, a literature review was carried out assessing their electrical efficiencies, operating pressures, operating temperatures, stack lifetime, load range, and CAPEX (**Table 1**). Overall, ALKE and PEME are expected to have similar electrical efficiency, operating pressure and temperatures. The main advantages of ALKE over PEME are the lower CAPEX and higher lifetime expectancy however current development on PEME are likely to achieve equivalent lifetimes than for ALKE in the near future. On the other hand, ALKE have lower operational load range than PEME. This characteristic will be further discussed on Section 2.2.1.

Table 1 – Literature review of typical specification of ALKE and PEME.

	ALKE	PEME	Reference
Electrical efficiency (%)	63 – 70	56 – 60	(IEA, 2019)
	60 – 80	60 – 80	(Lehner, et al., 2014)
	62 – 82	67 – 82	(Bhandari, et al., 2014)
Operating pressure (bar)	1 – 30	30 – 80	(IEA, 2019)
	< 30	< 200	(Lehner, et al., 2014)
	< 30	< 30	(Bhandari, et al., 2014)
Operating temperature (Celsius)	60 – 80	50 – 80	(IEA, 2019)
	60 – 80	60 – 80	(Lehner, et al., 2014)
	60 – 80	50 – 80	(Bhandari, et al., 2014)
Stack lifetime (h)	60,000 – 90,000	30,000 – 90,000	(IEA, 2019)
	60,000 – 90,000	20,000 – 60,000	(Bertuccioli, et al., 2014)
Load range (% relative to nominal load)	10 – 110	0 – 160	(IEA, 2019)
	30 – 150	0 - 200	(Lehner, et al., 2014)
	20 <	0 <	(Bhandari, et al., 2014)
CAPEX (EUR/kW)	460 – 1280	1000 – 1640	(IEA, 2019)
	760 – 1100	1200 – 1940	(Bertuccioli, et al., 2014)

Typical specifications of commercially available ALKE and PEME are also presented and compared in **Figure 2**. The list of commercially available ALKE and PEME used and their specifications are presented on **Appendix A**. Overall, commercially available ALKE and PEME agree with literature. They have same efficiency range and operational pressures (**Figure 2a**, **Figure 2b**). Moreover, both technologies presented similar specific energy consumption (**Figure 2c**). In other words, the amount of hydrogen produced is dependent on the nominal power installed rather than on the technology deployed. PEME also were confirmed to have a broader load range than ALKE (**Figure 2d**).

Figure 2 – Typical specifications of commercially available ALKE and PEME based on the list provided in Appendix A.

2.2 Electrolyser flexibility

The basis of power-to-gas and power-to-liquid energy storage systems is the variable operation of electrolysers to react to energy production or electricity price fluctuations. To discuss the operational flexibility of electrolysers to act in such a way some terminology definitions are required. A warm start is defined as start-up from heated stand-by or idle mode, which means that the system is held at operating temperature and pressure if necessary. A cold start is defined as start-up from ambient temperature after a long shut-down (Buttler & Spliethoff, 2018).

2.2.1 Load range

As can be seen in **Figure 2d**, ALKE are limited to a minimum load of 20-25% of nominal hydrogen production. This limitation is due to lateral diffusion of hydrogen across the membrane to the oxygen side resulting in a flammable mixture at low production rates (Raballo, et al., 2010). For PEME, most suppliers state no technical limit of minimum load because of the low gas permeability of the proton exchange membrane. In addition, PEME producers advertise the possibility of overload operation. However, degradation due to overload on long-term performance has yet to be investigated (Buttler & Spliethoff, 2018).

2.2.2 Variable operation

Overall, electrolysers can operate dynamically, being limited mainly by the time coefficients of external components and heat management. This ability is often quantified by the stack ramp-up and ramp-down times illustrated in **Figure 3 -Figure 6**. Both PEME and ALKE systems are reported to be able to vary their full load range from less than one second to few seconds. Mohanpurkar et al. realized load characterization tests of a 120 kW PEME stack for different load conditions. The electrolyser response times were less than 1 second in all load conditions (Mohanpurkar, et al., 2017). Eichman et al. investigated the operational flexibility of electrolysers by performing experimental tests on PEME and ALKE. Their work shows that the system-level response time for both the PEME and ALKE ramping up or down occurs quickly and is nearly complete after 0.2 second (Eichman, et al., 2014). Anderson et al. carried out several studies on a PEME stack under 60,000 hours lifetime. The stack was demonstrated to be well suited to grid support with response times less than a second (Anderson, et al., 2013). Commercially, Hydrogenics states that the response signal of both technologies can react in less than 1 second if already pressurized and operating at adequate temperature (Hydrogenics, 2019). A commercial PEME stack (SILYZER 300) is also reported by Siemens to be able to have a dynamic response of 10%/s from 0 to 100% (Siemens, 2019).

Figure 3 – Ramp-up test of a PEME under different load change conditions (Eichman, et al., 2014).

Figure 4 – Ramp-up test of an ALKE under different load change conditions (Eichman, et al., 2014).

Figure 5 – Ramp-down test of a PEME under different load change conditions (Eichman, et al., 2014).

Figure 6 – Ramp-down test of an ALKE under different load change conditions (Eichman, et al., 2014).

2.2.3 Warm and cold start

The reason why ALKE and PEME have to be kept in stand-by mode for flexible operation is mainly due to the required time for heat-up. Warm start-up time from heated and pressurised stand-by mode to full load is possible within 1-5 minutes for ALKE and within seconds for PEME (Buttler & Spliethoff, 2018). Mohanpurkar et al. performed load characterization tests of a 120 kW PEME stack for different load conditions. The electrolyser warm start times were in the order of 30 seconds and shutdown times less than 1 second. (Mohanpurkar, et al., 2017). Allidières et al. carried out experiments on a PEME stack during warm start. The study evaluated the ability of the PEME stack to satisfy the French requirements for primary and secondary power reserves, although they did not explore faster load variation of the electrolyser stack. Their experiments showed that the PEME stack was able to go from 100% to 75% in less than 30 seconds (primary power reserve requirement) and from 0% to 100% power in less than 2 minutes (secondary power reserve requirement) (Allidières, et al., 2019). Commercially, Hydrogenics states that the response signal of both ALKE and PEME can react in less than 3 seconds from a pressurized stand-by to 100% power (Hydrogenics, 2019). In addition, Siemens also reported a PEME stack (SILYZER 300) with a warm start of less than one minute (Siemens, 2019).

Electrolysers starting from a cold start exhibit a longer response time mostly because of the time the electrolyser requires to reach operating temperatures. PEME have much shorter heat-up times (around minutes) than ALKE due to the more compact designs and lower thermal capacity, while ALKE cold start times are in the range of hours (Buttler & Spliethoff, 2018). Mendaza et al. assessed the potential of ALKE and electrical vehicles to be used for power regulation. In their studies, ALKE were found to have starting times of about 2 hours (Mendaza, et al., 2013). Diéguez et al. carried out experiments on a 5kW ALKE and also reported heat-up times of more than 2 hours (Diéguez, et al.,

2018). In contrast, Eichman et al. performed tests on a 40kW PEME. From the off position to full power and hydrogen generation it took 6 minutes and 27 seconds. On the other hand, to shut down the unit, 1 minute and 3 seconds were required (Eichman, et al., 2014). In addition, Gemmer-Berkbilek carried out field tests on a 80kW PEME and the stack showed cold start times of approximately 5 min (Gemmer-Berkbilek, 2016).

2.3 System services requirements and electrolysers potential

A review of the current system services requirements in the context of Ireland was already carried-out in the deliverable D5.4 (Laguipo, et al., 2019). In this regard, **Table 2** shows the system services requirements according to EirGrid that is the current Transmission System Operator (TSO) in Ireland. Based on the discussions presented on Section 2.2, overall, both electrolyser technologies are capable of providing all system services. However, ALKE have to be kept operating all times in order be able to fulfil the ancillary services requirements while PEME are capable of provide all system services as long as it starts from a stand-by mode (warm start). **Table 3** presents a summary of the electrolyser operation flexibility highlighting their capability to provide all system services.

Table 2 – System services requirements in Ireland (EirGrid, 2018).

Service Name	Abbreviation	Requirements
Fast Frequency Response	FFR	2 – 10 sec
Primary Operating Reserve	POR	5 – 15 sec
Secondary Operating Reserve	SOR	15 – 90 sec
Tertiary Operating Reserve 1	TOR1	90 sec – 5 min
Tertiary Operating Reserve 2	TOR2	5 – 20 min
Replacement Reserve – Synchronised	RRS	20 min – 1 hour
Replacement Reserve – Desynchronised	RRD	20 min – 1 hour

Table 3 – Summary of electrolysers operation flexibility.

Operation condition	ALKE	PEME
Variable operation	0.2 sec (Eichman, et al., 2014) < 1 sec (Hydrogenics, 2019)	< 1 sec (Mohanpurkar, et al., 2017) 0.2 sec (Eichman, et al., 2014) < 1 sec (Anderson, et al., 2013) < 1 sec (Hydrogenics, 2019)
Warm start	1-5 min (Buttler & Spliethoff, 2018)	30 sec (Mohanpurkar, et al., 2017) < 30 sec (Allidières, et al., 2019) < 3 sec (Hydrogenics, 2019) < 60 sec (Siemens, 2019)
Cold start	2 hours (Mendoza, et al., 2013) 2 hours (Diéguez, et al., 2018)	< 7 min (Eichman, et al., 2014) 5 min (Gemmer-Berkbilek, 2016)

In this context, the main advantages of PEME over ALKE is their higher load range and their lower sensitiveness to cycling. PEME can operate at any part-load condition while energy prices are high and at overloads for short periods of time to maximize hydrogen production when balancing services are required. In addition, PEME presents no significant lifetime reductions due to load cycling (ITM Power, 2014), while discontinuous operation may induce additional degradation to ALKE (Mansilla, et al., 2011). Despite the higher operational capabilities of PEME, ALKE are still cheaper and a technical-economic analysis of both technologies needs to be carried out while building a business case for any electrolyser application.

3 Technical-economic comparison between batteries and electrolysers

Another option of a sustainable ancillary services provider is Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS). It is well established in the literature that batteries are technically capable of providing energy storage and frequency control (Su, 2018) and the actual installed power capacity of grid connected BESS is around 2.5 GW globally (GE Energy Consulting, 2018). Although both batteries and electrolysers can provide energy storage and balancing services, both technologies have important advantages and drawbacks that makes them compete in this market. Thus, a technical-economic comparison between both technologies is presented.

The vast majority of utility-scale battery systems installed in the U.S. over the past few years have been Li-ion, driven largely by cost reductions and power density achieved through electric vehicle manufacturing (NRECA, CFC, CoBank and NRTC, 2019). Hence, the report will only compare Li-ion batteries and electrolysers (PEME and ALKE).

3.1 Scale capacity

Although large scale stacks are commercially available for both electrolyser technologies, PEME are the actual preferred choice due to their compact design and the potential for cost reduction (Hydrogenics, 2019). Currently, large-scale ALKE and PEME plants are reported with capacities up to 20MW. However, no clear limitation exists for larger developments (Hydrogenics, 2019) (Green Car Congress, 2018).

Battery technology has undergone a huge expansion due to electrical vehicles research and development. Currently, the biggest Li-ion BESS in the world have capacity of 100MW (Neeon, 2019). Although BESS installed power capacity is higher than for electrolyser systems, BESS are limited to a few hours of energy storage potential, while the only time limitation of electrolysers systems is the hydrogen storage capacity.

3.2 Efficiency

Overall, the electrical efficiency of BESS is higher than for electrolysers systems. The electrical efficiency for ALKE, PEME and BESS is 56-72%, 46-69% and 85% respectively (**Appendix A**). It is worth mention that injecting electricity back to the grid from hydrogen produced from water electrolysis is not economically attractive at the current development level of electrolysers and fuel cells. The round-trip efficiency for electrolyser-fuel cell systems are around 30%, whereas BESS have round-trip

efficiencies of 75-90 (Pellow *et al.*, 2015). In addition, the current CAPEX for the development of such system is higher than for BESS. However, PEME and fuel cells still have a large potential for cost reduction and efficiency improvement, which may make them competitive in the future.

3.3 Lifetime

The life time of an alkaline electrolyser is reported to be up to 30 years, although a general overhaul is necessary every 7-15 years to replace/reactivate the electrodes and to replace the diaphragms (Bhandari, *et al.*, 2014). The balance of plant (BOP) lifetime of PEME is assumed to be 20 years and the stack lifetime of commercial systems are typically 10 years (Bareiß, *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, BESS have a high electrical efficiency (typically > 85 percent) and have a theoretical service life of 10 to 15 years. However, while theoretical models show a service life of 10-15 years, there has not been sufficient data to validate this and most projects are being built with 8-year service life (NRECA, CFC, CoBank and NRTC, 2019).

As previously discussed, the interest in using electrolysers and batteries to provide system services and operate under highly dynamic load profiles is a recent topic and precise experimental data are still not available. The main uncertainty is how degradation mechanisms act on those systems and their effect on system lifetimes. For ALKE, very few studies were found, although Mansilla *et al.* states that discontinuous operation may induce some additional degradation (Mansilla, *et al.*, 2011). ITM Power carried out experiments on PEME under intermittent current cycling. Their results show that Intermittent current cycling does not cause degradation on PEME (ITM Power, 2014). Sarasketa-Zabala *et al.* studied a realistic lifetime prediction approach for Li-ion batteries and degradation under different realistic dynamic operating conditions. Their experiments showed more than 10% capacity loss after 120 operating days (Sarasketa-Zabala, *et al.*, 2016). Ouyang *et al.* proposed a novel capacity degradation model that can simulate the degradation dynamics under varying working conditions for lithium ion batteries. Their results showed an average capacity loss of 20% after 1000 cycles (Ouyang, *et al.*, 2016).

3.4 Economics

Although several manufacturers already produce electrolysers, the market is still developing and identifying realistic cost and performance parameters is difficult (Hinkley, *et al.*, 2016). The recent study made by IEA reported prices ranging from 460 to 1280 EUR/kW for ALKE and from 1000 to 1640 EUR/kW for PEME. The report also indicates a shift from small pilot and demonstration projects to commercial-scale applications. This should start to create economies of scale that will help to drive down capital costs and to scale up the supply chain of the electrolyser industry (IEA, 2019).

Electrolyser operational costs (OPEX) found in literature are typically 2-5% of the initial capital expenditure (CAPEX) per year, excluding electricity and stack replacement costs. However, manufacturers emphasize that this number is very dependent on size (Bertuccioli, *et al.*, 2014). In addition, due to the market shifting from ALKE to PEME and the recent commercial development of PEME, there is considerable uncertainty regarding the lifetime and replacement costs for electrolyser stacks. The electrolyser stack is responsible for 50% and 60% of the CAPEX costs of ALKE and PEME respectively, although this may not represent actual stack replacement costs (IEA, 2019).

Strong research on battery technologies and the development within the electric vehicle industry and expanding global production capacity have induced a cost reduction of 85% since 2010 to an average of 160 EUR/kWh in 2018. The reduction is attributable to significant cost savings in both the battery cells and in the other components of the broader battery packs. The prices for the whole BESS are around 500 EUR/kWh (NRECA, CFC, CoBank and NRTC, 2019). Moreover, Hinkley et al. carried out a cost assessment of hydrogen production from PV and the OPEX was found to be approximately 0.75% of CAPEX costs (Hinkley, et al., 2016).

3.5 Summary of electrolysers and BESS characteristics

A technical-economic comparison between electrolysers and BESS was carried out regarding typical duration of energy storage, size, electrical efficiency, lifetime, cycling degradation potential, CAPEX and OPEX. **Table 4** summarise all the information discussed in Section 3.

Table 4 – Technical-economic comparison between ALKE, PEME and BESS.

Technology	ALKE	PEME	BESS
Typical duration	Hydrogen storage capacity	Hydrogen storage capacity	Up to 6h (NRECA, CFC, CoBank and NRTC, 2019)
Size	Up to 20MW¹ (Hydrogenics, 2019)	Up to 20MW¹ (Hydrogenics, 2019)	Up to 100MW (Neoen, 2019)
Electrical efficiency	63 – 70% (IEA, 2019)	56 – 60% (IEA, 2019)	85% (NRECA, CFC, CoBank and NRTC, 2019)
Lifetime	30 years (BOP) 7 – 15 years (stack) (Bhandari, et al., 2013)	20 years (BOP) 10 years (Stack) (BareiB, et al., 2019)	10 – 15 years (BOP)² (NRECA, CFC, CoBank and NRTC, 2019)
Cycling degradation potential ³	Medium (Mansilla, et al., 2011)	Low (ITM Power, 2014)	High (Ouyang, et al., 2016)
CAPEX	460 – 1280 EUR/kW (IEA, 2019)	1000 – 1640 EUR/kW (IEA, 2019)	500 EUR/kWh⁴ (NRECA, CFC, CoBank and NRTC, 2019)
Storage CAPEX	13 – 18 EUR/kWh (Hwang & Varma, 2014)	13 – 18 EUR/kWh (Hwang & Varma, 2014)	-
OPEX ⁵	2 – 5% CAPEX per year (Bertuccioli, et al., 2014)	2 – 5% CAPEX per year (Bertuccioli, et al., 2014)	0.75% CAPEX per year (Hinkley, et al., 2016)

¹ No clear limitations exist for scale up plants beyond 20MW;

² While theoretical models show a service life of 10-15 years, there has not been sufficient data to validate this and most projects are being built with 8-year service life;

³ Degradation from balancing services cycling profile is not a well-known phenomenon;

⁴ It is important to notice that the CAPEX for electrolysers is given in EUR/kW while for BESS is given in EUR/kWh;

⁵ OPEX does not consider batteries lifetime limitations or end-of-life stack replacements.

4 Conclusion and recommendations

Electrolysers have the ability to operate under variable conditions and to provide all system services categories as long as they keep operating at a minimum load. In the case of PEME the minimum load is a stand-by condition, while for ALKE is operating at around 20-25% load capacity. Both PEME and ALKE systems are reported to be able to vary their full load range from less than one second to few seconds. Warm start-up times for ALKE and PEME are up to 5 min and within seconds respectively, while cold start-up times are up to hours for ALKE and within minutes for PEME.

From the economical viewpoint however, there is no real interest to maintain the system in idle state. The current trend in the industry is to develop systems that can combine a power base-load operation (at nominal power condition) to a grid service capability. This can be done increasing operation loads, on top of the base-load, up to a maximum power value, when there is overproduction of electricity in relation to demand. In addition, electrolysers are able to operate at lower loads than the power base-load, up to a minimum power value when the electricity production is lower than demand. Operated in such a way, the water electrolysis unit remuneration can be obtained from both hydrogen production and grid services.

The main advantages of PEME over ALKE is their higher load range and their lower sensitiveness to cycling. Despite the higher operational capabilities of PEME, ALKE are still cheaper and a technical-economic analysis of both technologies needs to be carried out while building a business case for electrolysers to be used in system services. Current research is focusing on finding cost-effective ways to produce hydrogen and provide system services at the same time for example in hydrogen refuelling stations.

A technical-economic comparison between electrolysers and BESS was carried out. Energy storage with electrolyser is only limited by the hydrogen storage capacity while BESS are able to provide energy up to 6 hours. BESS have larger installed plants although no clear limitation exists for larger electrolyser plants deployment. Overall, the electrical efficiency of BESS is higher than for electrolysers systems. ALKE have the higher lifetime expectation followed by PEME. However, electrolysers and batteries subjected to dynamic load profiles is a recent topic and precise experimental data about degradation on these systems are still not available. CAPEX costs for ALKE, PEME and BESS are on average 870 EUR/kW, 1320 EUR/kW and 500 EUR/kWh respectively. OPEX is estimated to vary from 2 to 5% of CAPEX for electrolysers while for BESS is approximately 0.75% of CAPEX. However, PEME still have a large potential for cost reduction and efficiency improvement, whereas ALKE and Li-ion batteries are in a more mature development stage and no significant cost reduction and efficiency increase is expected.

Appendix A: Typical specifications of commercial electrolysers.

Table A - Overview of typical specifications of commercially available electrolysers. Adapted from (Buttler & Spliethoff, 2018)

Company (Country)	Model	H2 rate (Nm ³ /h)	Nom. Power (MW)	Max. Pressure (bar)	Spec. Energy Consumption (kWh/Nm ³)	Efficiency (%)	Load Flexibility (%)
ALKE							
ELB (DE)	LURGI SE	1400	6	30	4.3 – 4.65	65 – 70	25 – 100
Suzhou Jingli (CH)	DQ 1000	1000	4.7	16	4.7	64	10 – 110
IHT (CH)	S - 556	760	3.5	32	4.3 – 4.65	65 – 70	25 – 100
NEL Hydrogen (NO)	NEL A485	485	2.1	1	3.8 – 4.4	68	20 – 100
ELB (DE)	ELB ND4	480	2	1	4.3 – 4.6	71	25 – 100
Teledyne (US)	NH-450	450	2.7	10	5.9	51	17 – 100
ELB (DE)	BAMAG S200E	330	1.5	1	4.7	64	25 – 100
HT-Hydrrotechnik (DE)	EV 150	220	1.1	1	5.3	57	20 – 100
ETOGAS (DE)	-	62.5	0.3	15	4.8	63	10 – 110
Green Hydrogen (DK)	HyProvide A60	60	0.25	30	4.2	72	15 – 100
ErreDue (IT)	G2256	21	0.11	30	5.4	56	20 – 100
PEME							
Hydrogenics (CA)	HyLYZER-3000	300	1.5	30	5 – 5.4	56 – 60	1 – 100
Siemens (DE)	SILYZER 200	225	1.25	35	5.1 – 5.4	56 – 69	0 – 160
Proton OnSite (US)	M400	50	0.25	30	5	60	0 – 100
AREVA H2Gen (FR)	E120	30	0.13	35	4.4	68	10 – 150
Kobelco Eco-Solutions (JP)	SH/SL60D	10	0.06	8	5.5 – 6.5	46 – 55	0 – 100

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